

Supplemental material for research article by Pals et al., “Reservoirs and proposed transmission routes of *Staphylococcus aureus* related to intramammary infections in dairy goats: A scoping review”, published in Journal of Dairy Science.

Table 1. Search string systematic search intramammary and extramammary reservoirs of *Staphylococcus aureus* in dairy goats.

Search	Keywords	No. publications
CAB Abstracts on Ovid Platform 08-07-2025		
1	dairy OR milking.af	806,736
2	goat OR caprine.af	94,624
3	staphylococcus.af	128,614
4	aureus.af	106,484
5	1 and 2 and 3 and 4	997
Scopus 08-07-2025		
1	(TITLE-ABS-KEY ((dairy OR milking) AND (goat OR caprine)))) AND (TITLE-ABS-KEY (staphylococcus AND aureus))	372
CAB Abstracts and Scopus		1,369